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Research Article

**SURGICAL OUTCOME IN CASES OF SPONTANEOUS
SUPRA-TENTORIAL INTRACEREBRAL HEMORRHAGE**¹Dr. Samar Nawaz, ²Dr. Aqsa Younas, ³Dr. Easha Ahmed¹Lahore General Hospital, Lahore. samar25nawaz@gamil.com²Lahore General Hospital, Lahore. aqsasheikh3@gmail.com³Lahore General Hospital, Lahore. eashaahmed948@gmail.com**Abstract:**

Objective: To determine the frequency of surgical outcomes in cases with spontaneous supratentorial intracerebral hemorrhage.

Methodology: This descriptive case series study was done at Neurosurgery department of LGH, Lahore during January to September 2017. In this study the cases of both genders and age more than 20 years presenting with intra cerebral hemorrhage of supra tentorial region within last 7 days were included. The cases with GCS 15/15 and those with GCS less than 7, and those with associated AV malformation and ventricular extension of the bleed were excluded. Then these cases underwent evacuation of hematoma and were admitted for due period of time and were followed for 1 weekly where the outcome was seen in the form of mortality, volume of ICH and GCS status.

Results: In this study there were total 30 cases out of which 21 (70%) were males and 9 (30%) were females. The mean age at presentation was 53.57±9.21 year. There were 22 (73.33%) of cases with basal ganglia bleed as shown in table 01. After the surgical intervention mortality was seen in 4 (13.33%) of cases with p= 0.44. The mean volume of ICH pre and post procedure was 35.67±12.56 vs 8.11±2.34 with p= 0.01. The pre and post surgery GCS was 10.89±2.56 vs 13.67±2.89 with p value of 0.04

Conclusion: Surgical prognosis of ICH evacuation in supra-tentorial bleed is good and its significantly better in terms of reduction in volume of ICH and improvement in GCS.

Key Words: Supra-tentorial bleed, ICH, GCS

Corresponding author:**Dr. Samar Nawaz,**

Lahore General Hospital,

Lahore.

samar25nawaz@gamil.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Intracerebral hemorrhage (ICH) is one of the fatal conditions that are encountered in the Neurosurgical department and Emergencies. It is found in nearly 20% of the cases in the developed world and the data is lacking in the developing ones. It can result in a wide range of morbidities and also high number of mortality if untreated in time [1,2].

There are multiple risk factors that can lead to this bleeding and the most common one is Hypertension (HTN) associated arteriosclerosis, which is found accountable in nearly 80% of cases suffering from primary hemorrhages.³ The other common causes include arterio-venous malformations (AVF) and amyloid angiopathy. Poor controlled HTN is one of the most common and un-identified etiology [4,5].

The basic underlying pathophysiology is leakage of the blood through the small vessels i.e. perforating arteries due to persistent high blood pressure and that's why this ICH is found commonly in deep grey matter especially around basal ganglia and thalamus. Computed tomography (CT) brain is considered as the investigation of choice in this setting and is a tool rapidly detect it in initial phase [6].

The mainstay of the treatment is the evacuation of the hematoma which might not be done in every cases. clinical scenario, Glasgow coma scale (GCS) score, size of bleed and degree of deterioration are the important parameters that can direct for further management [7].

METHODOLOGY:**OBJECTIVE:**

To determine the frequency of surgical outcomes in cases with spontaneous supra-tentorial intracerebral hemorrhage.

Study settings;

Department of Neurosurgery, Lahore General Hospital, Lahore

Study duration;

January 2017 to September 2017

Study design;

Descriptive case series study

Sampling technique;

Non probability consecutive sampling

In this study the cases of both genders and age more than 20 years presenting with intra cerebral hemorrhage of supra tentorial region within last 7 days were included. The cases with GCS 15/15 and those with GCS less than 7, and those with associated AV malformation and ventricular extension of the bleed were excluded. Then these cases underwent evacuation of hematoma and were admitted for due period of time and were followed for 1 weekly where the outcome was seen in the form of mortality, volume of ICH and GCS status.

Statistical analysis;

The data was entered and analyzed by SPSS version 23.0. The categorical data was presented in terms of frequency and percentages and numerical data as mean and standard deviation. Post stratification chi square and independent sample t test were applied taking p value less than 0.05 as significant.

RESULTS:

In this study there were total 30 cases out of which 21 (70%) were males and 9 (30%) were females. The mean age at presentation was 53.57 ± 9.21 year. There were 22 (73.33%) of cases with basal ganglia bleed as shown in table 0I. After the surgical intervention mortality was seen in 4 (13.33%) of cases with $p= 0.44$. The mean volume of ICH pre and post procedure was 35.67 ± 12.56 vs 8.11 ± 2.34 with $p= 0.01$. The pre and post surgery GCS was 10.89 ± 2.56 vs 13.67 ± 2.89 with p value of 0.04 as shown in table II.

Table-I: DEMOGRAPHICS IN STUDY SUBJECTS

Demographics	Number	Percentage/ range
Age (years)	53.57 ± 9.21	45-67
Male	21	70%
Female	9	30%
Volume of ICH	35.67 ± 12.56	20-75
GCS	11.89 ± 2.56	8-14
Basal Ganglia	22	73.33%
Lobar	8	26.67%

Table II. SURGICAL OUTCOMES

Mortality		
Yes	No	p value
4 (13.33%)	26 (86.67%)	0.44
Volume of ICH		
Pre-surgery	Post surgery	p value
35.67±12.56	8.11±2.34	0.01
GCS		
Pre-surgery	Post surgery	p value
10.89±2.56	13.67±2.89	0.04

DISCUSSION:

Hypertension is an under rated factor leading to a lot number of cases with deadliest complications by affecting various organs like heart and brain. It can lead to leakage of the blood and result in fatal intra cerebral hemorrhage that can lead to deterioration of clinical scenario and a long term morbidity in such cases.

In this study out of 30 cases of ICH, basal ganglia were involved in 22 (73.33%) of cases while lobar area was affected in 26.67% of cases. this finding was similar to the results of the study done by Inagawa et al. where basal ganglia were involved in 67% of the cases and on further subdivision the putamen was affected in 34%, thalamus in 33% and lobar areas in 15% of the cases [8].

The pre and post surgery GCS was 10.89±2.56 vs 13.67±2.89 with p value of 0.04. This was also seen by the study done by Hossian et al where they revealed that there was significant improvement in the GCS after evacuation of hematoma and they further stratified that the cases that had GCS of 8 or less had poor prognosis and their GCS was not that much improved. The mortality in their study was observed in 31% of cases as compared to 4 (13.33%) of cases only in the present study.⁹ This difference can be explained by the factor that they included all the cases with ICH as compared to our study where were included only the cases that had GCS more than 7 and hence outcome was better. The mortality rate was seen in 54% of the cases in a study by Inagawa et al [8].

Broderick et al in another study; revealed the association of different parameters and they also stated that the cases with high pre operative volume of ICH and lower GCS score had a bad prognostic impact on mortality as well as recovery after the surgery [10].

The findings of the present study were also

supported by the STICH trial where they also found that the cases with GCS score of less than 8 had 91% risk of poor surgical outcome.¹¹ Yelmez et al. conducted also did not find any significant improvement in case with low GCS and the efficacy was seen in only 44% of the cases [12].

The mean volume of ICH pre and post procedure was 35.67±12.56 vs 8.11±2.34 with p= 0.01. This was also seen by the studies done in the past where there was significant improvement in volume after evacuation but the main impact on outcome was the GCS and initial amount of ICH [13,14].

CONCLUSION:

Surgical prognosis of ICH evacuation in supratentorial bleed is good and its significantly better in terms of reduction in volume of ICH and improvement in GCS.

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